

Mechanistic Study of Oxidation of Secondary Alcohols by *N*-Bromosaccharin in Presence of Saccharin

K. VIJAYA MOHAN, P. RAGHUNATH RAO and E. V. SUNDARAM*

Department of Chemistry, University College, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 1 October 1983, revised 22 August 1984, accepted 20 September 1984

Oxidation of secondary alcohols including cyclic alcohols by NBSacc has been carried out in presence of added saccharin (reduction product of NBSacc) and Hg^{2+} ions. The behaviour of substrates is anomalous, but irrespective of substrate the oxidant exhibits first order. Addition of acid catalyses the reaction and variable order in $[H^+]$ has been noticed. Among the 2-ols studied the order of reactivity observed is propanol < butanol < pentanol < octanol, and with cyclic alcohols the order is cyclopentanol < cycloheptanol < cyclooctanol. There is marginal decrease in rate with increasing percentage of acetic acid and increasing concentration of Na_2SO_4 . Corresponding ketone is reported to be the product of oxidation. The activation parameters have been calculated and the mechanistic conclusions are discussed.

ALTHOUGH NBSacc has been used in the preparative organic chemistry as oxidising and halogenating reagent¹, the mechanism of its oxidation of alcohols has not yet been established. However, its analogues *N*-bromosuccinimide², *N*-chlorosuccinimide³ and *N*-bromoacetamide⁴ have received substantial attention and several studies on the mechanism of their reaction have been reported in recent years. The different mechanistic pathways reported for these structurally related compounds prompted us to undertake this investigation. We report in this communication the results of rate measurements on the NBSacc oxidation of secondary alcohols including cyclic alcohols in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of saccharin. The mechanistic conclusions are also discussed.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and purified further either by recrystallisation or by distillation - acetic acid, butan-2-ol and pentan-2-ol (A.R., B.D.H.) cyclopentanol and cycloheptanol A.G., Fluka, cyclooctanol (Koch-Light), propan-2-ol and octan-2-ol (E. Merck). Acetic acid was refluxed over chromium trioxide. The middle fraction boiling at 117-118° (lit. 118.5°) was used. The oxidant was prepared by the bromination of saccharin by usual procedure¹.

The reactions were carried out in 60% (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture in the presence of 0.004 *M* $Hg(OAc)_2$ and 0.02 *M* saccharin at desired sulphuric acid concentration in the temperature range of 10-50°. During the oxidation of alcohols by NBSacc in acid medium, bromide and bromine are liberated *in situ*, which can be explained by the equations (1) and (2).

The liberated bromine may also oxidize alcohols. Hence, formation of Br_2 is suppressed by the addition of mercuric acetate⁵ which traps Br^- and forms an unionised $HgBr_2$ or $HgBr_2^{2-}$. It was observed that the pseudo-first order plots without added saccharin showed considerable departure from linearity after 20% of the reaction. This was attributed to the retarding effect of saccharin. However, with added saccharin the deviation from linearity disappeared and at the same time the rates were diminished. Therefore, we carried out all the reactions in the presence of added saccharin.

The kinetics of the reaction were followed by estimating unreacted oxidant iodometrically. All the experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions using ten-fold excess of [substrates] over the [oxidant] and in the presence of saccharin. The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by keeping the excess oxidant concentration over substrates and estimating the unreacted oxidant concentration from time to time.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be one mole of alcohol to one mole of oxidant as given by the equation (1). The products obtained were corresponding ketones which were identified by preparing the corresponding 2,4-DNP derivatives and comparing their melting points with the literature values⁶. Bromide ions were identified by the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [SUBSTRATE] ON OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS IN OXIDATION OF SECONDARY ALCOHOLS BY NBSACC

[NBSacc] = 0.002 M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 0.004 M, Aq. HOAc = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 45°
 [H₂SO₄] = 0.50 M, [saccharin] = 0.02 M

Alcohol	$k_{obs} \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at [substrate] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$							
	1.0	2.0	2.5	4.0	5.0	6.0	10.0	20.0
Propan-2-ol	2.72	4.62	5.82	8.01	9.36	11.0	15.4	28.4
Butan-2-ol	—	—	9.11	13.2	15.5	17.8	27.0	47.8
Pentan-2-ol	3.80	7.32	8.72	13.0	16.3	19.2	28.4	54.8
Octan-2-ol	—	9.53	11.9	20.4	26.5	32.4	54.8	127
Cyclopentanol*	4.41	9.97	13.5	22.6	29.2	35.7	—	—
Cycloheptanol*	14.8	30.7	—	56.8	—	101	—	—
Cyclooctanol*	24.8	51.2	64.6	97.6	133	—	—	—

*[H₂SO₄] = 0.05 M.

usual test. When acrylonitrile was added to the reaction mixture no polymerization was observed indicating that the reaction did not involve free radicals.

The order with respect to oxidant was found to be unity. The pseudo-first order rate constants increased with increasing alcohol concentration (Table 1). Plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs \log [substrate] are linear for all the alcohols studied, but slopes are not equal. Slopes are unity in the case of pentan-2-ol, octan-2-ol and all the cycloalcohols studied, whereas less than unity in the case of propan-2-ol and butan-2-ol. The order with respect to [saccharin] is fractional negative order (Table 2),

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [SACCHARIN] ON OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS IN OXIDATION OF SECONDARY ALCOHOLS BY NBSACC

[NBSacc] = 0.002 M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 0.004 M,
 Aq. HOAc = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 45°

Alcohol	$k_{obs} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at [saccharin] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$				
	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
Butan-2-ol*	2.33	1.83	1.46	1.32	1.22
Octan-2-ol*	3.34	2.65	2.35	2.13	1.89
Cycloheptanol**	3.65	3.07	2.26	2.02	1.97
Cyclooctanol**	8.34	5.11	5.11	4.26	—

*[substrate] = 0.05 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.50 M,

**[substrate] = 0.02 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.05 M.

which is confirmed from the linear plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs \log [saccharin]. The rate of oxidation was also enhanced with increase in sulphuric acid concentration, thus exhibiting acid catalysis. The dependence of rate on [H⁺] is found to be fractional from the linear plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs \log [H⁺]. The reactions were studied in the temperature range of 30 to 50°. The observed rate constants and activation parameters are recorded in Table 3. *N*-Bromosaccharin like other similar *N*-halo-compounds may exist in various forms in acid medium^{4,7}, namely free *N*-bromosaccharin, protonated *N*-bromosaccharin or Br⁺, and it can also exist as HOBr or H₂O⁺Br in acid medium. The different forms of reactive species for oxidant can be

TABLE 3—ORDER OF REACTIVITY AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN OXIDATION OF SECONDARY ALCOHOLS BY NBSACC

[NBSacc] = 0.002 M, Aq. HOAc = 50% (v/v),
 [Hg(OAc)₂] = 0.004 M, [saccharin] = 0.02 M

Sl. no.	Substrate	$k_{obs} \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at 35°	ΔH^\ddagger JK mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
1.	Propan-2-ol	3.43	69.3	105	102
2.	Butan-2-ol	6.85	69.3	99	99.9
3.	Pentan-2-ol	7.38	77.3	74	96.4
4.	Octan-2-ol	10.5	82.6	54	99.0
5.	Cyclopentanol	3.20	86.5	50	102
6.	Cycloheptanol	12.0	66.6	101	97.6
7.	Cyclooctanol	25.6	71.7	81	96.9

Sl. nos. : 1-4 [Substrate] = 0.05 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.50 M,
 5-7 [Substrate] = 0.02 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.05 M.

represented by the following equilibrium.

If free NBSacc is active species, there will not be any effect of saccharin on the rate of reaction. But our results show that saccharin inhibits the rate indicating that free NBSacc is not reactive species. If Br⁺, HOBr, and H₂O⁺Br are the active species the oxidation rate will be diminished by added saccharin which was observed in the present work. However, if Br⁺ and H₂O⁺Br are the active species the reaction should show acid catalysis. Our observations show that there is no acid catalysis in the absence of added saccharin, thus eliminating the possibility of Br⁺ or H₂O⁺Br being the active species. In the presence of added saccharin the oxidation process exhibits acid catalysis and is inhibited by saccharin, with fractional order dependence of rate with respect to [H⁺] as well as [saccharin]. In presence of added saccharin equilibrium (5) may be shifted towards left thus the formation of the protonated NBSacc may become important,

Taking all these facts into consideration protonated form of the oxidant along with HOBr are proposed as active forms of oxidant participating in the oxidation process. Therefore, in the presence of added saccharin and in sulphuric acid medium, we suggest the following mechanism in which the alcohol attacks the active species of oxidant in rate determining step.

Based on this mechanism the following rate expression can be obtained,

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{NBSacc}] = K_1 k'_1 [\text{NBSacc}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{alcohol}] + \frac{k_1 k_3 [\text{NBSacc}] [\text{alcohol}]}{k_2 [\text{saccharin}] + k_3 [\text{alcohol}]}$$

which explains fractional order dependence on [alcohol] and [H⁺] and inhibition by saccharin, while under the conditions of k₂ [saccharin] >> k₃ [alcohol], a first order dependence on [alcohol] which is observed in case of pentan-2-ol, octan-2-ol and cyclic alcohols.

An attempt has been made to evaluate the rate constants K₁k'₁ and k₁k₃/k₂ by studying the reactions at various concentrations of alcohol and H₂SO₄ (Table 4). Under the conditions k₂ [Sacc]

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF [OCTAN-2-OL] ON OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS [H₂SO₄]

[NBSacc] = 0.002 M, [saccharin] = 0.02 M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 0.004 M, Aq. HOAc = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 45°

[Octan-2-ol]	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹ at [H ₂ SO ₄]			
	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.8
0.025	0.78	1.01	1.19	1.92
0.05	2.02	2.13	2.65	4.04
0.10	2.95	3.75	5.48	9.50
0.20	5.82	7.68	12.8	21.3
0.25	7.99	9.59	19.2	29.6

>> k₃ [alcohol], a plot of k_{obs} vs [H⁺] gives a straight line with a slope equal to K₁k'₁ [alcohol] and intercept equal to (k₁k₃/k₂) [alcohol]/[saccharin]. A plot of slope vs [alcohol] and a plot of intercept vs ([alcohol]/[saccharin]) give straight lines passing through the origin with slopes to K₁k'₁ and k₁k₃/k₂, respectively. As

an example for octan-2-ol, the value of K₁k'₁ is equal to 0.635 × 10⁻² l² m⁻² s⁻¹ while k₁k₃/k₂ is equal to 37 × 10⁻⁶ s⁻¹. It has been observed that the oxidation of cyclic alcohols is faster than that of 2-ols. The observed rate constants (k_{obs}), K₁k'₁ and k₁k₃/k₂ values for cyclooctanol and octan-2-ol are given in Table 5. A perusal of rate data shows

TABLE 5—OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}), K₁k'₁ AND k₁k₃/k₂ VALUES FOR ALCOHOLS

[NBSacc] = 0.002 M, Aq. HOAc = 60% (v/v), [Hg(OAc)₂] = 0.004 M, [saccharin] = 0.02 M, [substrate] = 0.02 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.1 M, Temp. = 45°

Substrate	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	K ₁ k' ₁ × 10 ² l ² m ⁻² s ⁻¹	k ₁ k ₃ /k ₂ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
Cyclooctanol	7.6	8.00	3.98
Octan-2-ol	0.76	0.64	0.37

that cyclic alcohols react ten times faster than 2-ols. The K₁k'₁ and k₁k₃/k₂ values are also in accordance with rate data for both the alcohols. The K₁k'₁ and k₁k₃/k₂ values are proportional to k'₁ and k₃, respectively as K₁ and k₁/k₂ are the equilibrium constants and independent of the nature of alcohol. The ratio of k'_{1(cyclic alcohol)}/k'_{1(2-ol)} and k_{3(cyclic alcohol)}/k_{3(2-ol)} are 11 and 10 times, respectively which agree with our experimental results.

The data given in Table 3, show that under similar experimental conditions the order of reactivity is propan-2-ol < butan-2-ol < pentan-2-ol < octan-2-ol. Rate of oxidation increases with the increase of length of carbon chain. As the chain length increases the +I effect increases resulting in the enhancement of electron density at the hydroxyl bearing carbon atom.

The order of reactivity for three cyclanols studied is cyclopentanol < cycloheptanol < cyclooctanol. The rate is increasing with increasing ring size. Similar order of reactivity is observed in the oxidation of cyclanols by acid bromate^{8,9}, bromine¹⁰⁻¹² and NBS².

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (K. V. M.) wishes to thank C. S. I. R., New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

References

- J. N. BACHHAWAT and N. K. MATHUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1335.
- V. THIAGARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 809.
- N. S. SRINIVASAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1974, 30, 419.

MOHAN, RAO & SUNDARAM : MECHANISTIC STUDY OF OXIDATION OF SECONDARY ALCOHOLS ETC.

4. J. MUKHERJEE and K. K. BANERJI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1981, 46, 323.
5. J. C. BAILAR, "The Chemistry of Coordination Compounds", Reinhold, New York, 1956, p. 4.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Longmans Green, London, 1961, p. 346.
7. E. BISHOP and V. J. JENNINGS, *Talanta*, 1958, 197.
8. V. LAKSHMI and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 800.
9. V. LAKSHMI and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 567.
10. V. THIAGARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 830.
11. K. K. BANERJI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 244.
12. V. THIAGARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 149.